

RACE AND RACISM: THE VOICES OF AFRICAN AMERICAN WOMEN WRITERS

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Abstract

This paper aims to study the concept of race and racism, focusing on the manifestations of racial discrimination experienced by people of colour, as reflected in the narratives of contemporary African American women writers. Race is a dominant and widely accepted ideological discourse in Western thought. It is not only embedded in biological distinction but also socially constructed. This paper argues that racism is a threat to humanity. The theoretical framework draws on Ineke Van der Valk's concept of racism as an expression of group dominance, as articulated in her article *Racism: A Threat to Global Peace*, to critically examine how systemic power dynamics perpetuate racial hierarchies and inequities. This paper highlights that the pervasive threat of racism to humanity forms the basis of contemporary African American women writers' critiques of racism. Furthermore, the paper seeks to broaden the theoretical scope of International relations study, which has been critiqued for its white-centric and quantitative focus, by highlighting the importance of intersectional and inclusive approaches to global systems.

Keywords: Race, Racism, African American women writing

Introduction

African Americans constitute 12.6% of the population, approximately 38.9 million individuals, with an additional 3.1 million identifying as African American in combination with other races, bringing the total to

13.6% (42 million), according to the 2010 U.S. Census. Despite significant progress since the Civil Rights era, African Americans continue to face systemic racial discrimination and economic disparities (Minority Rights Group). For instance, reports from *The State of Black America* show that Black households had an average annual income of \$38,555, compared to \$63,155 for white households, illustrating a persistent economic divide (National Urban League report, 2018). This is reflected in the voices of African American writers and activists, which emphasize the need for continued social reform and greater equity.

Race is not only embedded in biological traits but is also a social categorization based on shared bodily or societal traits that are perceived as discreet within a given society. However, this concept underpins racism—the belief that certain races are superior to others. In *Racism, A Threat to Global Peace*, Ineke van der Valk argues that stigmatization plays an essential role in the marginalization of racial groups. She notes that the socio-psychological process of stigmatization, as described by Heatherton, Kleck, Hebel, and Hull (2000), is a common experience for socially excluded groups. Stigma often attaches to visible differences, which are deeply rooted in historical and cultural contexts. By the late 19th century, stigma became associated with medical pathology and marginalized groups, including those defined by race, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, and physical or cognitive differences (Davis, 1995; Garland-Thomson, 1997). This highlights an intersection between race and stigma, with later scholars extending the concept of stigma to include people with disabilities, showing how these groups are similarly subjected to social exclusion.

The concept of “racism” is relatively modern compared to the notion of race. The term is often attributed to Magnus Hirschfeld, a German Jewish scholar, who is recognized for its first scientific application in his 1938 book critiquing racial ideologies (Wodak and Reisigl, 2000: 43; Miles, 1993: 29). In Western Europe, “racism” began appearing in dictionaries during the 1930s and has since been a subject of significant academic debate and theoretical contestation. Scholars have noted the absence of a universally accepted definition of racism (Van den Berghe, 1967: 9-11; Memmi, 1994: 105-133), a gap reflective of the fluid and context-dependent nature of racial constructs. Historical studies

demonstrate that the concept of race has been shaped by varying sociopolitical and cultural frameworks across different national and temporal contexts (Goldberg, 1993; Hannaford, 1996). Similarly, the understanding of racism has evolved, underscoring its dynamic and constructed character. This definitional fluidity is not unique to racism but is also evident in other systemic social hierarchies, such as sexism. Sexism can be described as an ideological apparatus that asserts the superiority of one sex over another. It involves discrimination; bias, stereotyping, and harassment rooted in gender and are most commonly directed at women and girls.

The voices of African American women began to gain attention through their writings during the Civil War and Reconstruction eras, leading to widespread recognition during the Harlem Renaissance of the 1920s. Cultural and political movements were shaped by women writers, who played pivotal roles in the Civil Rights and Women's Rights Movements of the 1960s, continuing their influence into contemporary times. They not only reflect the historical struggles and triumphs of Black people but also provide profound insights into the complexities of race, gender, and class. Writers like Anna Julia Cooper, Toni Morrison, Maya Angelou, and Alice Walker employed realism to authentically depict the lives of women and their communities, capturing both personal and collective experiences of resistance and resilience. The scholarship of African American studies can be traced in the critical works of Kimberlé Crenshaw, bell hooks, Patricia Hill Collins, and Angela Davis. All of these have interrogated systemic oppression, shedding light on the interconnectedness of racial, gendered, and class-based inequalities in the voice of American women's writing.

Primary Texts

The focus of this study revolves around a detailed analysis of four primary texts from the select readings:

Toni Morrison's first novel, *The Bluest Eye* (1970), offers a profound critique of systemic racism. The narrative centres on the devastating experiences of Pecola, an eleven-year-old African-American girl. The story delves into how Pecola's racial identity and self-worth are eroded by the internalization of Eurocentric beauty standards and the pervasive white supremacist ideology that dominates her environment. The story,

set in 1941 during the Great Depression in Lorain, Ohio, Morrison's hometown, incorporates personal accounts of experiences, adding depth and authenticity to its portrayal of racial and social struggles.

The seminal text *Ain't I a Woman: Black Women and Feminism* (2015) by bell hooks explores the intersection of race, class, and gender differences. She illustrates how sexism affected Black women during slavery, the undermining of Black womanhood, and the racial biases within the modern feminist movement. She proposed that without addressing these intersections, the rhetoric of sisterhood in the feminist movement is incomplete.

In her seminal article *Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex* (1989), Kimberlé Crenshaw, a legal scholar, critically reflects on how Black women's oppression was often overlooked in both feminist and anti-racist movements. She proposes that a person is shaped by various social, political, and personal aspects that overlap at intersections, much like a traffic system. She challenges the simplistic narrative of inequality in the case of Black women and proposes intersectionality as an analytical framework to understand the uniqueness of individual experiences.

Maya Angelou's memoir *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings* (1969) is a critique of systemic racism during the civil rights movement. The memoir traces the personhood of Maya, from three-year-old Maya to the seventeen-year-old mature voice of a single mother, which is interconnected with race, class, and gender. It is a first-person narrative story that deals with the inner psychology of Maya, her suffering, oppression, and depicts a realistic picture of the society in which she was born, ultimately reclaiming her identity.

Rationale of study

This study emphasizes the fundamental principle that, despite racial differences, all individuals share a common humanity. It critically examines racism as an unscientific ideology, perpetuating unfounded beliefs in genetic superiority and inferiority. The study explores how racial prejudice disrupts societal harmony by weakening communal bonds, eroding core values essential for peace, undermining solidarity, and overshadowing love and sincerity within communities.

Aims and objectives of study

This study aims to study the concept of race and racism through Ineke Van der Valk's political discourse framework within critical race studies, focusing on the intricate connections between racial constructs and the dominance of hegemonic groups. Drawing on Ineke Van der Valk's argument in *Racism, A Threat to Global Peace*, it analyses how racism undermines global peace and security while functioning as a form of social inequality rooted in historical and structural mechanisms of systemic dominance, particularly regarding gender, class, and ethnic identity. Furthermore, the study aligns with the perspectives of African American women, emphasizing that racism operates not only as overt prejudice but also as a systemic, institutionalized, and dynamic force shaping social relations and practices. Through textual analyses of literary works, the study explores the profound socio-economic and cultural impacts of racism.

Research questions

1. What is race? How has the concept of race evolved, and what is the contemporary landscape of racial constructs? How do the intersections of class and gender shape and reinforce racial hierarchies?
2. What is racism? How does the systemic nature of racism function as both an ideology and an instrument of dominance by hegemonic groups?
3. What are the economic dimensions of racism, and how have they been constructed and perpetuated through historical and structural contexts?

Argument and structure of the paper

This paper argues that racism is a fundamental threat to humanity. The paper delves into three key ideas central to understanding racism as an expression of dominance. First, it analyses Ineke Van der Valk's discourse on race, shedding light on the systemic and structural nature of race, aligning it with critical analysis of Toni Morrison in *The Bluest Eye* (1970). Second, it explores racism as an expression of dominance, examining the intersection of race, gender, and class through the critical works of bell hooks in *Ain't I a Woman: Black Women and Feminism*

(2015), Kimberlé Crenshaw in *Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex* (1989), and the literary work of Maya Angelou in *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings* (1969). Finally, it amplifies the voices of African-American women, analysing their enduring and powerful responses to racism across time, which contribute to a broader theoretical understanding of American Studies and its relationship with International Relations studies.

Keywords: Race, Racism, African American women writing

Analysis:

The term “race” originated in the 16th century, initially referring to a nation or ethnic group. Etymologically, it signified a category of people with a common ancestry and was adopted into English from Old French *rasse* (1512) and Italian *razza*. The Oxford English Dictionary traces its earliest usage to the mid-16th century, describing it as a “group of people belonging to the same family.” The concept of race as a way to classify anatomically modern humans has a long history in Europe and the Americas (Wikipedia). Ineke van der Valk traces the understanding of race to its historical and socio-scientific evolution, highlighting three key meanings: humanity consists of diverse groups with distinct physical traits, each group has different origins, and racial boundaries hold cultural and social significance (Bulmer and Solomos, 1991). By the late 19th and early 20th centuries, race shifted from a descriptive categorization to a politically charged ideology used to justify inequalities, notably under Nazi rule. After World War II, international organizations, including UNESCO in 1950, declared race a social myth, not a biological reality.

UNESCO's 1950 Declaration redefined race as “not so much a biological” reality but rather a “social myth,” fundamentally challenging traditional views on human differences. The declaration refers to specific historical atrocities such as slavery, genocide, colonialism, and apartheid, where racial ideologies were deployed to justify violence, oppression, and suffering on a massive scale. The harmful misunderstanding of race, both culturally and within societal narratives, has caused profound damage, including the loss of human lives, widespread discrimination, marginalization, and systemic inequalities across societies. One can trace how the residual effects of racial

ideologies continue to persist in modern forms of racism. Consequently, systemic racism and discrimination hinder the potential of millions by denying them equal opportunities for education, work, and participation in society. The declaration further advocates for the social acceptance that “the biological differences between ethnic groups should be disregarded” in matters of social policy, interactions, and institutions. It emphasizes embracing the fundamental “unity of mankind.” From a biological perspective, all humans belong to the same species, as Montagu (1963: 172) explains, and from a social perspective, explored by Shipman (1994: 156-170), this reflects the consensus of social scientists at the time: race as a biological concept is unsubstantiated, and its societal implications are harmful.

However, UNESCO's statement advocated replacing the term race with the more neutral term ethnic group, which refers to a group of people considered to share similarities in one or multiple ways (Wikipedia). Consequently, many scientific studies dropped the concept of race and adopted neutral terms like ethnic group. African American writers retained the concept of race in their writings, reflecting on how they have been victimized by racial discrimination over time.

Race is a concept created by society (Schuster, 1995), functioning as a discursive category that relies on a vague set of physical traits, such as skin colour and hair texture, to distinguish social groups (Hall, 1992b: 298). According to Toni Morrison, physical beauty, “was not simply something to behold; it was something one could do.” She emphasizes the performative nature of beauty. In *The Bluest Eye*, Morrison critiques racial ideology through the Breedlove family: Pecola's mother, Pauline, who is told by her White employer, “You are ugly people,” and her father, Cholly, scarred by racist experiences in his youth. The Breedloves are rejected by society due to their appearance, and Morrison explores how the demonization of an entire race affects vulnerable members, especially female children. This internalized racism drives Pecola to desire, “Each night without fail, she prayed for blue eyes.” The Breedloves' crippling self-esteem stems from the belief that they are inherently ugly.

The story of Pecola Breedloves, the protagonist, is narrated by Claudia MacTeer, reflecting on her childhood and evolving understanding of

race and identity, while the omniscient narrator provides background on other characters. Pecola's mother, Pauline, develops a concept of femininity influenced by White actresses like Jean Harlow. Geraldine, a woman from a middle-income household, feels burdened by her Blackness, while Soaphead Church denies his Black identity. Pecola is exposed to images reinforcing White beauty standards, such as Shirley Temple and Mary Jane on candy wrappers, illustrating the community's role in her suffering.

Toni Morrison uses eyes as a central metaphor to critique racism and its impact on identity and societal beauty standards. A metaphor evokes deeper ideas about identity and societal norms. The title, *The Bluest Eye*, underpinned the superlative form of blue eye colour, reflecting society's idealization of Eurocentric beauty. Pecola becomes obsessed with having blue eyes and eventually descends into madness. Early in the narrative, the narrator reveals Pecola's painful realization that her eyes, which "held the pictures and knew the sights," are central to her perception of herself. Pecola internalizes societal rejection, believing that "if those eyes of hers were different, that is to say, beautiful, she herself would be different." This highlights how Eurocentric beauty standards impose a profound burden on marginalized individuals, particularly young girls, forcing them to deny their individuality. The impact of this internalized racism is evident in Pecola's fixation on the phrase: "Pretty eyes. Pretty blue eyes. Big blue pretty eyes" (page 33). The repetition emphasizes Pecola's obsessive desire to attain the unattainable ideal of blue eyes, exposing the destructive impact of Eurocentric beauty standards on self-identity.

Toni Morrison's *The Bluest Eye* was published (1970) at a crucial juncture in the history of the American civil rights movement. It is significant to note that the setting of the story is against the background of 1940-41, the beginning of World War II for the United States. Morrison provides a vivid, realistic picture of a girl in a Black community whose loss of innocence is caused by her father within her own home, which highlights the gendered violence on a girl's body. Pecola's tragedy is not only the result of racism but also of a community and family that fail to provide her with the nurturing she needs. Claudia realises how she and her community are responsible for Pecola's mental state. Claudia says, 'All of our waste, which we dumped on her and

which she absorbed' (153). Thus, the story highlights the contemporary manifestations of racism within the human, socio-economic, and cultural landscape.

The evolution of "racism" is commonly described as a relatively modern concept, evolving during the European age of imperialism, transformed by capitalism and the Atlantic slave trade, of which it was a major driving force. The racial segregation in the United States in the 19th and early 20th centuries and apartheid in South Africa are well documented and serve as reference points in studies and discourses about racism. Across disciplines, scholars have examined how racism historically fuelled numerous genocides, such as the Holocaust (1933–1945), the Armenian Genocide (1914–1918), the Rwandan Genocide (1994), and the genocide of Serbs in 1995 in the Independent State of Croatia. They also explored how racism was a cornerstone of colonialism and racial imperialism, exemplified by European colonization in the Americas, Africa, and Asia, which involved the exploitation and subjugation of indigenous populations. It has played a significant role in the forced population transfers during the Soviet era, which involved the deportation of indigenous minority groups (Wikipedia). It also highlights how Indigenous peoples and enslaved individuals, in particular, have endured persistent racist attitudes and systemic discrimination throughout history.

Racism is a complex social phenomenon. Theories of racism differ across disciplines, including economics, sociology, and social psychology, as each field develops its understanding of the phenomenon based on its specific frameworks. Consequently, a universally agreed-upon definition remains elusive. As Goldberg aptly states, "so there is no single explanation for racism, for there is no single racism to be explained" (1993: 209). Defining racism merely as bigotry, inequity, discrimination, or prejudice against people based on their race or ethnicity is overly simplistic. The expression of racism can be traced in social actions, nativism, xenophobia, otherness, segregation, hierarchical ranking, supremacies, and related social phenomena. It can be a political ideology or a human perception that supports the expression of bigotry or inequity in discriminatory practices in society. This ideological framework underpinning a racist mind-set, behaviours, and practices often assumes that humans can be divided into distinct groups with

differences in social behaviour, innate cognitive abilities, and physical capacities, all of which can be ranked as either inferior or superior. It also refers to violations of racial equality based on equal opportunities (Wikipedia).

Ineke van der Valk argues that racism operates as an expression of group dominance, while the Systemic nature of Racism emphasizes that racism is not confined to individual prejudices but is embedded in social systems. The role of racial discourse, through discursive representations, imbues social practices with meaning and legitimizes social inequality, which is particularly insightful. The economic dimensions of racism, situated in historical and contemporary contexts, align with Black feminist writings.

The seminal text *Ain't I a Woman: Black Women and Feminism* by bell hooks, particularly in Chapter 4, "Racism and Feminism: The Issue of Accountability," reflects on the contemporary feminist movement, which failed to acknowledge the historical "oppression of black women" and "rhetoric of sisterhood" is superficial in nature. She notes that the conflict between Black and White women began during slavery, not the 20th-century women's movement, with racism being a dominant force. White women, due to racial imperialism, have contributed to the division within the feminist movement. Historically, Black women have been denied full recognition, left in underpaid labour, and their struggles ignored, even by White women in the feminist movement. hooks explores the intersection of race, gender, and class in American history, highlighting activists like Mary Church Terrell, Sojourner Truth, Anna Cooper, and Amanda Berry Smith, who fought against the invisibility and marginalization of Black women. Truth's argument that the rights of Black men were prioritized while Black women were overlooked reflects the on-going gender-based oppression, where black women were left subordinate to Black men. The systemic nature of racism highlights that it extends beyond individual biases and is deeply ingrained in social structures (Van Dijk, 1993: 18-48). Hooks draws a parallel between these historical struggles and the current feminist movement, emphasizing that freedom from racial oppression is incomplete without freedom from gender-based oppression.

bell hooks critiques the intersection of racism and sexism in American society. She argues that white supremacist ideologies have historically positioned whiteness as the norm and defined “woman” as synonymous with “white woman” (168). This ideology not only marginalizes and dehumanizes women of colour, labelling them as “dehumanized beings” and “others,” but also denies them the dignity, agency, and rights afforded to white women. These systemic structures reinforce the idea that only white women fully embody the term “woman,” while Black women are identified as “others” in the dominant white feminist narrative, and they remain subordinate to Black men. As a result, women of colour are denied full recognition of their humanity and womanhood and become subjected to dual forms of discrimination, both as women and as Black women.

In the 1960s and 1970s, African American women expanded the intersectional framework to highlight how systems of oppression, such as racism and sexism, interact and overlap, creating compounded forms of discrimination. In her article *Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex*, Kimberlé Crenshaw critiques how social movements, such as feminist, anti-racist, and labour movements, often focused narrowly on single categories of inequality. The historical movement is crucial for understanding how racism adapts to different economic and socio and political conditions (Miles, 1993b; Wilson, 1996). Crenshaw highlights the lynching of Black males in the United States, frequently justified by the claim of protecting White women’s sexuality. Crenshaw argues that this institutional practice was rooted in the racist myth that Black men posed a sexual threat to White women, a stereotype used to uphold white supremacy and control both Black and White communities. Crenshaw says that emphasis on protecting White women’s sexuality often centered Black men in narratives about racial violence, overshadowing the sexual abuse and violence experienced by Black women.

Crenshaw critiques how “sexist expectations of chastity,” which idealized women as pure and modest, were predominantly applied to White women, thereby excluding Black women. This exclusion was powerfully contested by Sojourner Truth in her 1851 speech, “Ain’t I a Woman?”, where she challenged dominant notions of womanhood shaped by White, middle-class norms and recounted the horrors of slavery: “I have born thirteen children, and seen most of 'em sold into

slavery, and when I cried out with my mother's grief, none but Jesus heard me—and ain't I a woman?" She highlights the particular impact of these gendered and radicalized norms on Black women.

The expression of racism can be traced in Maya Angelou's writing. Social inequality is deeply intertwined with structural mechanisms of group dominance, particularly in relation to gender, class, and ethnicity. Maya Angelou's memoir *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings* metaphorically portrays a racially divided society, split between Black and white, and male and female. Through her experiences in the Black community of Stamps, Angelou illustrates the pervasive racial hierarchies and vividly depicts individuals with racist tendencies, emphasizing the harshness of white Southern attitudes toward African Americans. Angelou also portrays the economic hardships faced by African Americans in the South, highlighting the daily labour of Black families in a segregated economy: "the fingers cut by the mean little cotton balls." Poverty and exploitation were widespread. Maya's early encounters with racial discrimination included denial of basic health services. For instance, when Maya experiences a toothache, the white dentist refuses to treat her, stating, "I'd rather stick my hand in a dog's mouth than in a nigger's." This event reflects the entrenched racism of the era, where African Americans were dehumanized and deprived of basic rights. Angelou also emphasizes the resilience of Black communities in the face of such oppression. Her grandmother, Momma, stands as a figure of fortitude, guiding Maya in navigating a world that consistently seeks to marginalize them.

Maya Angelou's narration highlights the pervasive social segregation that left most Black children with little understanding of White people's appearances. Education plays a vital role in Maya's personal development, as the memoir begins with a first-person narrative, delving into Maya's inner psychology while presenting a realistic portrayal of the society in which she was born and eventually reclaims her identity. The story spans from Maya's childhood at age three to her becoming a mother at sixteen. Early in the narrative, Maya internalizes the belief that beauty is inherently linked to Whiteness, yearning to be "white, white, white," convinced that her worth could only be realized by possessing white features. However, by the conclusion of the memoir, Maya undergoes a significant transformation. One of the memoir's central

themes is the pervasive influence of racism and segregation. At her graduation, Maya is insulted by a White speaker who demeans the aspirations of African-American students. Reflecting on this, Maya recalls, “the boys...would try to be Jessie Owens and Joe Louis.” This moment of defeat is countered by an act of collective resistance when valedictorian Henry Reed leads the audience in the “Negro National Anthem,” restoring their pride and confidence. Maya realizes:

“I was no longer simply a member of the proud graduating class of 1940; I was a proud member of the wonderful, beautiful Negro race.”

In contemporary times, the voices of African American women serve as a bridge to understanding individual reflections on movements such as feminism, anti-racism, and labour rights, highlighting their shared struggles against systemic oppression. The voices of women such as Sojourner Truth, Zora Neale Hurston, Maya Angelou, Alice Walker, Jamaica Kincaid, bell hooks, Kimberlé Crenshaw, Angela Davis, and Patricia Hill Collins provide a critical lens through which to understand its mechanisms and effects. These contemporary writers give voice to unheard or unrecorded voices of women activists, who have shaped the literary history of African American literature with a legacy of slavery narratives, struggle, resilience, protest, and triumph over oppression.

Toni Morrison made significant contributions to African American literature and became the first African American woman to receive the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1993. She meticulously portrayed the historical horror and suffering of enslaved women, using their stories to shed light on contemporary issues of discrimination and marginalization based on race and gender in both her fictional and non-fictional works.

bell hooks explores her experiences as a woman of colour navigating predominantly White feminist and academic spaces throughout her writings. She states, “I was not being taught about the ways race shaped female identity.” She critiques how the traditional American education system, curriculums and feminist discussion failed to address how race influences the identity and experiences of women. She recounts that when she tried to highlight how race and racism shaped her life differently from that of White women; her concerns were often ignored or met with disdain. She observes that these racial differences were met with resistance even in “consciousness-raising groups,” which were

intended to foster solidarity and mutual understanding within academic settings. She critiques the disposition of white women “eager to bond around shared notions of sisterhood” (168), arguing that this collective sisterhood focused solely on common experiences of gender oppression while ignoring the intersection of racism. This exclusion reflects how feminist movements often centred White women’s issues, marginalizing the voices of African American women.

Maya Angelou’s memoir, *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings*, not only reflects her personal experiences with racism and oppression but also resonates with the historical and political struggles of women of her time. In Chapter 25, Maya says, “They don't really hate us. They don't know us. How can they hate us?” Throughout her writings, she uses personal accounts, expressions, and personae to illustrate how oppression and individual experiences are interrelated.

The voices of African American women, despite different visions, share foundational principles within Black feminism, such as the inseparability of racism, sexism, and classism. Their aspirations and perspectives differ from those of Black men and White women. Since the 1980s, the voices of African American women have continued to resonate globally, reflecting the universal struggle for justice and equality, the desire for freedom and dignity, while celebrating the richness of African American culture through writing. The voices of African American women offer valuable insights into International Relations and Peace Studies, providing an intersectional framework advanced by Kimberlé Crenshaw to understand how states and other actors operate within the global contexts of gender and the international system.

Conclusion

Race is a social construct, and racism, as a process of ideological marginalisation, operates on ideological, institutional, and structural levels. Van der Valk highlights the historical evolution of racial discourse, rooted in intellectual shifts that replaced religious and rational explanations of human differences with concepts of descent and heredity. The dynamic framework of racism is manifested in the contemporary landscape of racism, as depicted in Toni Morrison’s *The Bluest Eye* and Maya Angelou’s *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings*. Both works explore how racial and biological characteristics become

powerful markers of oppression, highlighting the social and psychological impacts of racism on individuals and communities.

Similarly, the critical works of bell hooks and Kimberlé Crenshaw reveal the historical roots of racial hierarchy, discrimination, conflict, and the multiple layers of marginalization faced by Black women. Their advocacy for an intersectional framework highlights the importance of understanding the human condition through an intersectional lens. The voices of African American women intertwine race, class, gender, and community experiences with broader socio-political commentary, offering literary reflections on the enduring impacts of racism and systemic discrimination. One key argument of this study is that racism represents a profound threat to humanity, underlying all of these analyses and revealing the deep, pervasive nature of racial injustice in society.

Moreover, the intersectional framework of Black feminism can significantly contribute to the study of International relations by highlighting the essential role of Black women in advancing gender equality and inclusivity within global policy frameworks. This perspective not only addresses how race, gender, and class intersect in shaping global policies but also highlights minority perspectives in policy discussions. In this context, it becomes clear that racism is not simply a local or personal issue but a global concern deeply intertwined with justice, equality, and human dignity.

This paper can further open new avenues for examining international foreign policy, particularly in the way the United States addresses racial discrimination and economic disparities, both domestically and abroad. By exploring U.S. foreign policy through an intersectional lens, one can assess whether it adequately responds to these systemic issues and actively works toward rectifying global injustices tied to race.

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